

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**NURSES ROLE IN EMERGING THREATS AND PANDEMIC
PREPAREDNESS**

**Anwar Fahad Alkhamis, Aisha Ahmed AlQuhaydan, Nweer Salman Alkhalidi, Hibah
Fareed Aldhaif, Ali Ahmed Alkhulif, Huda Baqer Aljubarah, Woud Eid Al Otaibi**
King Abdulaziz Hospital - National Guard health affairs – Al Hasa – Saudi Arabia

Abstract:

Nurses play a vital role in pandemic preparedness and response, serving as frontline caregivers and leaders in health systems. Their effectiveness hinges on adequate training, resource access, and organizational support. This response synthesizes key aspects of the nursing role in addressing emerging threats and pandemics.

Keywords: nurse, pandemic, role

Corresponding author:

Anwar Fahad Alkhamis,
King Abdulaziz Hospital
- National Guard health affairs – Al Hasa – Saudi Arabia

QR code

Please cite this article in press Nouf Abdulaziz Alnosair et al, **Nurses Role In Emerging Threats And Pandemic Preparedness**, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2023; 10 (06).

INTRODUCTION:

Emerging threats and pandemics are primarily characterized by the emergence of infectious diseases that are either newly identified, newly recognized, or increasing in prevalence in new areas. These diseases, often referred to as emerging infectious diseases (EIDs), pose significant challenges to public health and basic science due to their unpredictable nature and rapid spread. (1, 2) A critical aspect of emerging threats is the phenomenon of antimicrobial resistance (AMR), which complicates the treatment of infections and is increasingly recognized as a major public health threat. The rise of drug-resistant pathogens, such as those causing tuberculosis and malaria, highlights the urgent need for robust public health policies and effective antibiotic stewardship. (1, 3) Additionally, the emergence of new pathogens, including those that have adapted to human hosts, underscores the importance of surveillance and response strategies to mitigate outbreaks and pandemics. (4, 5) The historical context reveals that while some diseases are newly recognized, others have re-emerged due to various factors, including demographic changes and increased global travel. (1) Moreover, the proliferation of biological weapons capabilities, driven by advances in biotechnology, presents a unique and unpredictable dimension to emerging threats, raising concerns about bioterrorism and the potential misuse of biological research. (6) Collectively, these characteristics illustrate the complex landscape of emerging threats and pandemics, necessitating a multifaceted approach to public health preparedness and response.

The Role of Nurses in Pandemic Preparedness

Nurses play a critical role in managing emerging threats and pandemics, with key responsibilities centered around patient advocacy, infection control, and multidisciplinary collaboration. One of their primary duties is to advocate for patients, ensuring their needs are met during crises, particularly in the context of emerging infectious diseases. This advocacy extends to influencing health policies at local, regional, and national levels, which is essential for effective disease prevention and management. Infection control is another vital responsibility for nurses, who must establish and adhere to rigorous standards to prevent disease transmission. This includes implementing surveillance measures and educational programs that enhance public safety. (7) During pandemics, nurses are on the front lines, providing care while also protecting themselves and their patients from infection. They must be adept at using personal protective equipment (PPE) wisely and practicing medical distancing to minimize exposure. (8, 9) Moreover, nurses must be prepared to manage

the unique challenges posed by infectious disease outbreaks, which require not only clinical skills but also the ability to work collaboratively in multidisciplinary teams. This collaboration is crucial for shaping effective public health policies and ensuring comprehensive care for vulnerable populations, such as cancer patients during a pandemic. (7, 9) Overall, the combination of advocacy, infection control, and teamwork underscores the essential skills nurses must possess to navigate the complexities of emerging health threats.

Challenges Faced by Nurses in Emerging Threats

pandemic has significantly exacerbated workforce issues and burnout among nurses, presenting a multifaceted challenge that requires urgent attention. Frontline nurses reported moderate levels of burnout, characterized by emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, which are critical indicators of mental health strain during this crisis. (10) The increased patient load, with 62% of nurses experiencing heightened stress due to a rise in the number of patients per nurse, has further intensified feelings of burnout. This situation is compounded by workforce shortages, as the pandemic has led to a significant reduction in available nursing staff, placing additional pressure on those who remain. (11, 12) Moreover, acknowledging the physical and emotional toll on nurses is essential for understanding these workforce challenges. Without proper recognition and support, nurses are at risk of substantial psychological issues, which can lead to burnout and attrition from the profession. The need for systemic organizational responses and supportive nursing teams is critical to mitigate these effects and enhance the resilience of the nursing workforce. (13) Policymakers and healthcare organizations must prioritize interventions that address these issues, including providing adequate resources, mental health support, and fostering a supportive work environment to ensure that nurses can effectively respond to emerging threats and pandemics. (11, 12, 14)

Best Practices and Strategies for Nurses in Pandemic Response

In responding to pandemics, several best practices and strategies for nurses have emerged as critical for effective patient care. First, maintaining safe staffing levels is essential, as research indicates that hospitals with better-staffed nursing teams achieve superior patient outcomes, particularly during crises like COVID-19. This is complemented by the establishment of supportive professional environments that empower nurses to utilize their knowledge and skills fully, which is vital for

coordinating care and disaster response. (15) Additionally, the expanded use of advanced practitioners, facilitated by regulatory changes from the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid, has proven beneficial. By reducing supervision requirements, these changes allow for better utilization of nursing resources, thereby enhancing the overall healthcare response. (15) Collaboration and teamwork among nursing staff are also crucial, as supportive nursing teams are essential for delivering quality care during a pandemic. (13) Furthermore, fostering a positive ethical climate within healthcare institutions helps manage ethical stress and concerns among nurses, which is particularly important in high-stress situations. (15) In general a multifaceted approach that includes safe staffing, supportive environments, expanded roles for advanced practitioners, teamwork, and a positive ethical climate can significantly enhance the effectiveness of nursing responses during pandemics. These strategies not only improve patient outcomes but also support the well-being of nursing professionals.

REFERENCES:

1. Mayer JD. Emerging Diseases: Overview. In: Heggenhougen HK, editor. *International Encyclopedia of Public Health*. Oxford: Academic Press; 2008. p. 321-32.
2. Laperche S. Definition of emerging infectious diseases. 2011;6(1):112-5.
3. Dabke G, Sheridan E. Antimicrobial resistance: the threat to public health. 2011;131(6):260-.
4. Greenfield RA, Bronze MS. Emerging Pathogens and Knowledge in Infectious Diseases. *The American Journal of the Medical Sciences*. 2010;340(3):177-80.
5. Woodland DL, Winslow GM. Immunity to emerging pathogens. 2008;225(1):5-8.
6. Lindler LE, Choffnes E, Korch GW. Definition and Overview of Emerging Threats. In: Lindler LE, Lebeda FJ, Korch GW, editors. *Biological Weapons Defense: Infectious Diseases and Counterbioterrorism*. Totowa, NJ: Humana Press; 2005. p. 351-9.
7. Capitulo KL, Korniewicz DM, Baldwin CM. Are Emerging Infectious Diseases the Most Significant Global Health Concern for Nurses? *MCN: The American Journal of Maternal/Child Nursing*. 2012;37(5).
8. Usher K. Editorial: Are we ready? Preparing nurses to respond to disasters and emerging infectious diseases. 2010;19(11-12):1483-4.
9. Nuryani SNA, Lisnawati LGJBN. Nurse's roles in protecting cancer patients during COVID-19 pandemic. 2020;4(1):25.
10. Hu D, Kong Y, Li W, Han Q, Zhang X, Zhu LX, et al. Frontline nurses' burnout, anxiety, depression, and fear statuses and their associated factors during the COVID-19 outbreak in Wuhan, China: A large-scale cross-sectional study. *eClinicalMedicine*. 2020;24.
11. Galanis P, Vraika I, Fragkou D, Bilali A, Kaitelidou DJJoan. Nurses' burnout and associated risk factors during the COVID-19 pandemic: A systematic review and meta-analysis. 2021;77(8):3286-302.
12. Pourteimour S, Yaghmaei S, Babamohamadi H. The relationship between mental workload and job performance among Iranian nurses providing care to COVID-19 patients: A cross-sectional study. 2021;29(6):1723-32.
13. Fernandez R, Lord H, Halcomb E, Moxham L, Middleton R, Alananzeh I, et al. Implications for COVID-19: A systematic review of nurses' experiences of working in acute care hospital settings during a respiratory pandemic. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. 2020;111:103637.
14. Hardiyono H, Aiyul I, Ifah F, Wahdaniah W, Reni FJREI. Effect covid-19: Burnout on nurse. 2020;798:1015.
15. Lake ET. How effective response to COVID-19 relies on nursing research. 2020;43(3):213-4.